

Investigating the Effect of Creative Mathematical Reasoning Tasks on Student Achievement: A Causal Inference Machine Learning Approach.

Nathan McJames^{1,2}, Andrew Parnell^{1,2}, and Ann O'Shea²

¹Hamilton Institute, Maynooth University

²Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Maynooth University.

In this study we investigate the impact of regularly assigning creative mathematical reasoning tasks on student achievement. Using a causal inference machine learning approach applied to Irish eighth grade data from TIMSS 2019, we find that assigning challenging questions requiring students to go beyond the instruction has a clear positive effect on mathematics achievement. Asking students to decide their own problem-solving strategies is also found to have a positive effect. In contrast, frequently asking students to practise procedures on their own is not associated with a positive increase in achievement. These results were consistent across all three cognitive domains of “knowing”, “reasoning”, and “applying”. We therefore recommend the incorporation of creative mathematical reasoning tasks into most classes by teachers as an effective way to improve student achievement.

Keywords: creative mathematical reasoning, causal inference, TIMSS

Introduction

A growing body of research demonstrates the importance of students working on problems which require them to think creatively and develop their own problem-solving strategies. However much of the work to date has been based on small studies. In this paper, we will examine the effectiveness of regular exposure to creative reasoning tasks using data from an international large-scale assessment, namely the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS 2019). Our study employs a causal inference machine learning approach based on Bayesian Causal Forests (BCF, Hahn et al., 2020). We apply our model to Irish eighth grade data from TIMSS 2019, and attempt to answer the following research questions: 1) What is the effect on achievement of regularly assigning creative mathematical reasoning tasks to students, and 2) How does this effect change across the three TIMSS cognitive domains of “knowing”, “reasoning”, and “applying”?

Literature Review

Lithner's (2008) framework describes two ways in which students can approach problems in mathematics. The first, called imitative reasoning can be further divided into two distinct types: memorised reasoning and algorithmic reasoning. Memorised reasoning refers to situations where a student can recall a complete solution and need only transcribe their answer without any further thought. Algorithmic reasoning is applied in situations where students instead recall a full procedure or algorithm from similar problems they have seen previously, and may follow the necessary steps to arrive at a solution, often requiring only trivial calculations to proceed from step to step. Lithner argues that the reliance of students on imitative reasoning can be a hindrance to the development of deeper levels of mathematical understanding, as the recollection of solutions and completion of procedures can be

performed with very little “conceptual insight into what they [are] doing” (Lithner, 2008, p. 259).

When no complete solution or algorithm can be recalled, students must employ creative mathematical reasoning (CMR). CMR requires students to respond to novel situations by creating their own problem-solving strategies, with “plausible” mathematical arguments used to justify or support their choices (Lithner, 2008). Research has shown that students presented with tasks requiring CMR tend to perform better on tests (Lithner, 2017). Studies by Jonsson et al. (2014) and Wirebring et al. (2015) which involved assigning students to groups with either an algorithmic reasoning or creative mathematical reasoning focus to learning both found that students in the CMR group outperformed their peers in a test after the study.

Despite the many benefits of CMR, research has shown that much of the emphasis in textbooks is focused primarily on algorithmic reasoning, and that students are rarely given a chance to engage with problems requiring CMR. A review by Jäder (2020) of mathematics textbooks in twelve countries for example, showed that up to 90% of tasks could be solved by students reusing existing templates, or making only minor modifications to example solutions. Work by Mac an Bhaird et al. (2017) shows that this reliance on algorithmic reasoning tasks is also common in undergraduate service mathematics courses in Ireland.

Methodology

Data and Sample

The Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS 2019) is an international large-scale assessment which has taken place in many countries across the world every four years since 1995. As part of the study, students in the fourth and the eighth grade (fourth class of primary school and second year of secondary school in Ireland) are given a short assessment in mathematics and science to estimate their achievement level in these subjects. Participating eighth grade students also complete a short questionnaire on aspects such as confidence in mathematics, how many books and educational resources they have at home, the highest level of education received by their parents, and many others. The eighth-grade subset of the 2019 data provides a representative sample of 4118 second year students, with an average age of 14.4 years. Additionally, the 565 mathematics and science teachers, and school principals of these students complete a short questionnaire on teaching practices, years’ experience, and other school related factors. The combined dataset therefore provides a rich source of information on student, teacher, and school characteristics.

Creative Mathematical Reasoning Questions

To investigate the effect of regularly assigning tasks requiring CMR, we used the data arising from the following questions answered by teachers: “How often do you do the following in teaching this class?” 1) “Ask students to complete challenging exercises that require them to go beyond the instruction”, 2) “Ask students to decide their own problem solving procedures”, 3) “Ask students to practice procedures on their own”. The possible

responses to these questions were: 1) “Every or almost every lesson”, 2) “About half the lessons”, 3) “Some lessons”, or 4) “Never”.

These questions tie in closely with the features of creative mathematical reasoning from Lithner’s (2008) framework. Asking students to decide on their own problem-solving procedure requires them to reason creatively about which strategies are best suited to a particular problem. Also, asking students to complete tasks which require them to “go beyond” the instruction means they cannot rely on template solutions or examples studied in class previously, requiring a creative solution to tackle an unfamiliar problem. Practising procedures, however, is more closely linked to preparing students for tasks requiring imitative reasoning. Of course, there will be a degree of subjectivity regarding what constitutes deciding a problem-solving strategy, or what going “beyond” the instruction means, but we believe the teacher’s responses to these questions provide valuable insights into how regularly their students have opportunities to practise creative mathematical reasoning.

Cognitive Domains of Achievement

In addition to assessing overall student achievement in mathematics, TIMSS includes a specific evaluation of student performance in the three cognitive domains of “knowing”, “reasoning”, and “applying” (Mullis et al., 2017). Achievement in the “knowing” cognitive domain reflects a student’s ability to recall and recognise facts as necessary when working on a mathematics problem. High achievement in the “reasoning” domain requires students to demonstrate they can analyse, evaluate, and draw conclusions from mathematical situations, providing mathematical arguments to justify their decisions. Finally, students who perform well in the “applying” domain can successfully apply mathematical facts, rules, and procedures to both real life and purely mathematical problems.

Given the focus of CMR on presenting students with novel tasks in unfamiliar situations, requiring them to creatively develop their own problem-solving strategy, we expect the “reasoning” domain to be more strongly influenced by the frequency at which teachers assign CMR tasks to their students. Similarly, as the “knowing” and “applying” domains are focused primarily on recalling and applying mathematical facts to familiar situations, we expect these domains may be less subject to influence from engagement with CMR tasks.

Bayesian Causal Forests

Our analytical approach in this study is based on an advanced causal inference machine learning algorithm called Bayesian Causal Forests (BCF, Hahn et al., 2020). BCF is a tree-based model, meaning it learns from the data by creating a set of decision rules which provide a pathway from the root of a tree to its terminal nodes. At the terminal nodes a prediction for each data point is provided. Figure 1 gives a visual example of a single decision tree from a BCF model. While this example appears quite simple, it is important to note that the size of the trees in a BCF model can increase or decrease in size depending on the complexity of the relationships among variables in the dataset. Moreover, the predictions made by a BCF model are typically based on the contributions of many decision trees which work together to each explain a small part of the variability in the outcome variable. In this

way, BCF can capture very complicated relationships and interactions among variables in the data.

Figure 1

An example of a decision tree.

Unlike most machine learning models, BCF is capable of disentangling the causal effect of a specific factor from the impact of other confounding variables that are not of primary interest. The standard implementation of BCF is only applicable to a single outcome variable at a time, and only to situations where the factor of interest takes just two levels. Therefore, in order to apply BCF to the multiple cognitive domains of “knowing”, “reasoning”, and “applying”, we will use the multivariate BCF extension developed by McJames et al. (2023) and make an extra modification allowing for the inclusion of multiple treatment levels. Our model in this study can be summarised as follows:

$$y_{i,j} = \mu_j(x_i) + \tau_{j,1}(x_i)Z_{i, \text{half of lessons}} + \tau_{j,2}(x_i)Z_{i, \text{every lesson}} + \epsilon_{i,j}$$

In this formula, the Z_i values are dummy variables which indicate if a student belongs to the “half of lessons” or “every lesson” categories, and x_i represents the known characteristics associated with student i such as age, gender, socioeconomic background, the experience of their teacher, and many others. In total, each x_i comprises more than forty student, teacher, and school characteristics which we control for. The response $y_{i,j}$ is the achievement of student i in cognitive domain j , and μ_j provides the prognostic contribution of the variables we are not primarily interested in. Each τ_j represents the effect on cognitive domain j of receiving creative mathematical reasoning tasks with the specified frequency provided by Z_i , and $\epsilon_{i,j}$ is a random error term. The predictions from the μ_j and τ_j parts of the model are provided by decision trees, such as the example in Figure 1.

Results

A breakdown of the teachers’ self-reported responses can be found in Table 1 below. Of the 565 teachers in the sample, 46 teachers did not provide a valid response due to not being administered the questionnaire or failing to answer the relevant questions, so 519 valid responses were obtained. Interestingly, asking students to practise procedures on their own, which is most closely related to the category of imitative reasoning, is much more common than the two CMR task types.

Table 1

Creative mathematical reasoning frequency. 565 teachers. 519 valid responses.

How often do you do the following in teaching this class?	Never	Some Lessons	Half the Lessons	Every lesson
Ask students to complete challenging exercises that require them to go beyond the instruction.	3.2%	33.1%	38.5%	25.2%
Ask students to decide their own problem-solving procedures.	5.4%	40.3%	35.3%	19.0%
Ask students to practise procedures on their own.	0.3%	7.4%	20.2%	72.1%

Figures 2, 3 and 4 provide a visual representation of our results. The boxplots depict the credible intervals for the average treatment effects of using different question types at varying frequencies. We have constructed these boxplots such that the central body corresponds to a 50% credible interval, and the full extent of the whiskers covers a 95% credible interval for the estimated effect sizes. Overall mathematics achievement in Ireland follows an approximately normal distribution with an average of 524 and a standard deviation of 73. Therefore, an effect size of 7.3 would correspond to a 0.1 standard deviation increase in achievement. Effect sizes of this magnitude are common in education research and can be thought of as being medium in size (Kraft, 2020).

Figure 2

Effect of regularly asking students to go beyond the instruction

Looking at Figure 2, we see that relative to never, or only sometimes assigning challenging questions which require students to go “beyond” the instruction, there is a clear positive effect of assigning questions of this type in about half of the lessons. This positive effect is increased when the frequency of assigning the challenging questions becomes every or almost every lesson. A similar pattern can be seen in Figure 3 which shows the estimated effects of regularly asking students to decide their own problem-solving procedures. In

contrast, Figure 4 shows that asking students to practise procedures on their own in “about half of the classes” or “about every class” is likely to have a negative effect on student achievement. While the effect sizes across the cognitive domains are very similar in all three cases, note that the positive effect of asking students to complete challenging questions is consistently higher than the positive effects of asking students to decide their own problem-solving strategy, suggesting this may be even more beneficial for improving student achievement.

Figure 3

Effect of asking students to decide their own problem-solving strategies

The similarity of the effect sizes across the three cognitive domains and the overall achievement scale is surprising. We might have expected that engaging in creative mathematical reasoning would have less of an effect on the “knowing” domain, which is focused on memorising rules, procedures, and facts. If we look very closely at Figures 2 and 3, a very small difference in the effect sizes is visible, with the magnitude of the effect on the knowing domain slightly smaller than the other three domains, but this difference is too small to be significant. With more data and an increased sample size, greater differences across the cognitive domains may begin to be discernible with greater precision, however.

Figure 4

Effect of asking students to practise procedures on their own

Discussion

Our results which identify the positive effect of regularly assigning tasks requiring creative mathematical reasoning are in line with previous studies by Lithner (2017), Jonsson et al. (2014), and Wirebring et al. (2015). Our finding that frequently assigning tasks focused on algorithmic reasoning is likely to decrease achievement also supports these studies by highlighting the negative effect of relying too heavily on tasks of this type. Of the factors we investigated, the most beneficial impact was associated with assigning challenging questions which require students to go “beyond” the instruction. We emphasise, however, that tasks do not need to be difficult to encourage creative mathematical reasoning (Lithner, 2008). There only needs to be an aspect to the question, which is novel, requiring more thought than simply reusing previously studied solutions or algorithms.

Our short study makes two important contributions. Firstly, the studies mentioned previously included small, non-representative samples of students, and therefore the results from our study which uses a large representative sample of students from Ireland are more generalisable. Second, unlike the post-study tests used in these existing studies, our results are based on a standardised international mathematics assessment, and therefore provide an added amount of interpretability. For example, an effect size of nine on the TIMSS overall achievement scale corresponds to the difference between the mean mathematics achievement levels of students in Ireland (524) and the United States or England (both 515).

Based on these results, we encourage teachers to place a higher emphasis on assigning CMR tasks to their students. Only 19.0% of teachers in the sample reported asking students to decide their own problem-solving strategies every or almost every lesson, and only 25.2% reported assigning questions that go “beyond” the instruction at the same frequency. Therefore, given the positive effect that this can have on student achievement, we encourage all teachers to incorporate such questions in most classes where possible. This is especially important given previous findings which show that students are unlikely to be presented with CMR tasks in standard mathematics textbooks (Jäder, 2020). An opportunity therefore exists for teachers to help fill this gap.

Some limitations of this study include that our results only apply to eighth grade student data from Ireland. Additional studies based on data from other countries or grade levels would therefore be necessary to improve the generalisability of our findings. It is also important to note that the BCF model we have used makes a number of important assumptions. Crucially, the model assumes we have accounted for all possible sources of confounding. However, while we have strived to control for as many confounding variables as we can, it is certainly possible that some important confounding variables might not have been collected as part of the TIMSS study. Finally, as we noted earlier, the question given to teachers on how often they ask students to “go beyond” the instruction is somewhat subjective. This should be borne in mind when interpreting our results, as teacher specific reporting differences may exist.

Potential avenues for future research include the application of a similar method to investigate the effect of other teaching practices, such as how often teachers use mixed or same ability grouping during class time, or how often teachers use various strategies such as relating new concepts to a student's prior knowledge. Given TIMSS includes data on student achievement in both mathematics and science, a similar investigation focused on science achievement would also be of interest. Alternatively, using data from PISA may provide valuable insights.

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